

DIGITAL ECONOMY AND ITS IMPACT ON ECOLOGY

Khusanboyeva Tursunoy Mukhammadkasimdjanoyna

Andijan Machinebuilding institute,

Trainee-teacher of the "Economics" department,

Egamberdiyev Shavkatbek Shahobiddin o'g'li

Andijan Machinebuilding institute, student Tel: +998911752964

Email: shavkatbekegamberdiyev79@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10579064>

Annotation:

This article contains opinions about industrialization, economic growth processes and their impact on the environment, the field of environmental economics, some modern problems of environmental economics and their solutions.

Key words: digital economy, electronic, ecological environment, pollution, technology, environment.

INTRODUCTION

Digital economy is a set of digital goods and services produced and sold as a result of economic activities closely related to e-business and e-commerce based on digital technologies. It is sometimes referred to as the internet economy, the new economy, or the web economy. The digital economy significantly improves people's living standards, which is its main benefit. The digital economy is the main link of corruption and "black economy". Because numbers seal everything, store it in memory, provide information quickly when needed. In such conditions, it is impossible to hide any information, make secret deals, not to provide full information about this or that activity, the computer will reveal everything. A large amount of information and systematicity does not allow for lies and fraudulent activities, because it is impossible to cheat the system.¹

The current stage of economic development is characterized by the acceleration of the digitization process, in which the innovative infrastructure of countries plays a decisive role. Globalization of the economy, which began at the end of the last century, helped to create and develop many institutions of national power, as a result of which the possibility of remote influence on domestic state administration appeared. It requires national governments to take into account the international rules set and presented by supranational institutions and various groups of regional integration bodies, which will not

¹ https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Raqamli_Iqtisodiyot

only change the current situation and fate of many countries of the world, but also cause serious pressure and economic impact. shows. The impact affects the well-being of the population living in the area both directly and indirectly. When studying well-being at the level of the world economy, it can be noted that all countries of the world are uneven in their development, in some countries the issue of survival is acute, in others, the majority of the population lives in relative prosperity. The world's national institutions of higher power are constantly faced with the task of balancing these two opposite poles and creating new living conditions in which people will live long, happy, healthy and creative lives. The well-being of the population consists of the ability of each individual country to ensure a decent standard of living in its territory. Many governments are trying to improve the standard and quality of life of their citizens. The assessment of the well-being of the population is possible through studies conducted by various world rating agencies, which show the course and economic policy of the country.²

After the digital economy entered people's views, the relationship between the digital economy and the ecological environment became the focus of attention of scientists. He pointed out that the digital economy has improved the structure of energy consumption by optimizing the industrial structure, thus limiting air pollution. This effect was more pronounced in developed regions. They found that this result can be applied to the surrounding areas as well. Some studies have shown that the digital economy can also increase the level of green innovation in cities to improve clean manufacturing technology. However, different conclusions have been put forward that the development of the digital economy is not beneficial for the ecological environment in all regions. In regions that have not yet reached the inflection point of the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC), the development of the digital economy unexpectedly increased the demand for electricity in the short term, thereby increasing the consumption of fossil fuel resources.³

The digital economy can effectively improve environmental performance. The research of scientists in various fields on the digital economy and environmental indicators can be divided into two areas: the impact of the digital economy on saving resources and the impact of the digital economy on reducing pollution. On the one hand, it is noted that the development of the digital economy has increased the level of production technology, which has led to a

² <https://infocom.uz/raqamli-iqtisodiyotning-aholi-farovonligiga-tasiri/>

³ <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2022.969878/full>

reduction in energy consumption. In particular, digitalization of production processes allows manufacturers to better manage consumables, including energy and production materials. Computer science and technology can help planning departments allocate these resources more efficiently and avoid wasteful production activities. In addition to the manufacturing sector, digital technology can also affect the distribution sector. With the help of Internet technologies, logistics efficiency has been significantly improved. Transactions between buyers and sellers have become much easier. This greatly stimulated market consumption. Unlike traditional distribution and sales activities, the data element serves as a vehicle for these operations, and its costs are almost negligible. In other words, the resources previously spent on this part of consumption were saved. At the same time, digitization has emphasized the role of communication technologies in economic activity. Some unnecessary trips and meetings will be replaced by electronic communication, reducing the energy consumption of economic cooperation activities. This shows that the development of the digital economy can be effective in saving resources and improving energy efficiency. Another aspect is the mechanism by which the digital economy can reduce pollution. The development of the digital economy by production can effectively alleviate the problem of information asymmetry. This led to greater mobility of technological factors and encouraged collaboration and innovation in production technology. This means that manufacturers will be more efficient and polluting emissions will be reduced during the production process. In particular, manufacturers can use platforms such as the Internet to quickly exchange technical issues, form stable partnerships, and expand the added value of their products. According to Porter's hypothesis, manufacturers can spend this capital on research and development. This leads to more refined and cleaner production techniques. Similarly, digitization has given rise to many new forms of environmental regulation. For example, with the help of Internet of Things (IoT) technology, it is possible to monitor the situation related to the generation and processing of pollutants in real time. The production department can use their feedback to adjust the production scale. This technology can also be used to collect and analyze environmental monitoring data, using cloud computing to quickly access environmental pollution data in an area. On this basis, the quality of the environment and the emission of pollutants are analyzed. This will help the

government to limit the excess emissions of some enterprises in a timely manner.⁴

The development of the digital economy plays an important role in improving the level of individual health and improving environmental pollution. Many literatures examine the relationship between the digital economy and environmental pollution or the digital economy and public health.

The connection between the development of the digital economy and environmental pollution is studied. According to the theory of ecological modernization, digital technologies can alleviate environmental problems, which provides a theoretical basis for studying the role of the development of the digital economy in improving environmental pollution. In practice, with the emergence of the energy crisis and the increasing demand for sustainable human development, improving the impact of digital technologies on the ecological environment has become the focus of society. We review the existing research and find that many scholars have conducted in-depth research on the relationship between the digital economy and environmental sustainability, but their views differ. Most scientists agree that the digital economy can improve the quality of the environment. For example, the research carried out by Ozcan B. and Ishida H. showed that in the development of the digital economy, relevant sectors can reduce environmental pollution by optimizing production processes, increasing the efficiency of technological innovations and reducing energy consumption. Lin B. focused on the impact of the digital economy on air pollution emissions and found that the digital economy can reduce carbon emissions through industrial modernization and technological innovation. In addition, the technological effects inherent in the digital economy in traditional production can encourage enterprises to make full use of modern technologies and promote structural dividends for environmental improvement; this environmental improvement effect is manifested not only in accelerating the rate of local emission reduction. With the deepening of research, some scientists have found that there may be "green blind spots" in the development of the digital economy, for example, some studies believe that the digital economy is based on Internet technology, and the excessive use of such technology will increase the consumption of resources and energy in daily life. life and production to the detriment of improving the quality of the environment. Although the digital economy is a new economic form, due to the specific

⁴ <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2022.969878/full>

characteristics of its industry, the information technology used can have negative consequences for wasting resources and damaging the environment.

Despite the controversial relationship between the digital economy and environmental pollution mentioned above, most scholars have not completely denied the role of digital technologies in improving the environment. In general, with the deep integration and application innovation of digital technologies in the resources, energy and environment sectors, the digital economy will be able to reshape production systems, promote the digitization of industry, and directly or indirectly reduce energy consumption in the production sector. improvement of environmental quality and development of social and ecological stability. The relationship between environmental pollution and public health has been widely studied at home and abroad. Some scientists believe that environmental pollution is an important cause of some chronic diseases. For example, environmental pollutants including heavy metals, air pollutants, phthalates and melamine have been found to increase the risk of chronic kidney disease in the population. In some cities, increased industrial sulfur dioxide emissions lead to increased lung cancer and respiratory disease deaths in local and neighboring areas. In addition to the negative effects of air pollution on respiratory diseases, it also has a negative effect on cardiovascular diseases and sleep quality. In addition, polluting emissions are one of the burdens of health care costs in the region and the country. For example, the Global Long-Term Dynamics Study of Health Expenditures and Environmental Pollution found that for every 1% increase in carbon dioxide emissions, each country's health costs increase by 2.5%. In many developing countries, economic growth is accompanied by increased energy consumption, which ultimately leads to poor air quality that threatens human health.⁵

Summary.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, yuqoridagi olimlar asosan atrof-muhitning ifloslanishi aholining sog'lig'ining pasayishiga olib keladi va turli jismoniy va ruhiy kasalliklarni keltirib chiqaradi va aholining sog'lom hayot sifatini yaxshilash uchun mintaqaviy hukumatlar tegishli sog'liqni saqlash xarajatlarini ko'paytiradi degan fikrga qo'shiladilar. Yuqoridagi adabiyotlarni ko'rib chiqish ushbu maqola uchun raqamli iqtisodiy rivojlanish, atrof-muhitning ifloslanishi va aholining sog'lig'i o'rtasidagi munosabatlarni o'rganish uchun yaxshi nazariy asos yaratadi, o'tgan tadqiqotlar asosan ikkitasi o'rtasidagi munosabatlarga qaratilgan. Bundan tashqari, bir nechta olimlar atrof-muhit ifloslanishining

⁵ <https://bmcpublihealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-023-15788-4>

raqamli iqtisodiyot va aholi salomatligi o'rtasidagi vositachilik rolini o'rganadilar. Raqamli iqtisodiy rivojlanishning aholi salomatligiga ta'sirini o'rganishda raqamli iqtisodiy rivojlanish ko'pincha internetga kirish, internet foydalanuvchilari va axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish kabi yagona ko'rsatkichlar bilan o'lchanadi. Afsuski, yangi iqtisodiy shakl sifatida raqamli iqtisodiyot hali ham rivojlanish darajasini har tomonlama o'lchash uchun yagona standartlarning etishmasligi, o'lchov indeksleri nafaqat raqamli infratuzilmani, balki raqamli chiqish, raqamli sanoat va raqamli dastur kabi boshqa o'lchamlarni ham o'z ichiga olishi kerakligini, bir nechta olimlar raqamli iqtisodiy rivojlanishning aholi salomatligiga fazoviy ta'sirini o'rganishdi. Nazariy jihatdan, raqamli texnologiyalarning paydo bo'lishi sanoat resurslaridan foydalanish va aholining sog'liqni saqlash faoliyati bo'yicha fazoviy masofaning cheklovlarini zaiflashtirdi. Bundan tashqari, raqamli texnologiyalarni qo'llash mintaqalar aholisi uchun Real vaqtda sog'liqni saqlash bo'yicha maslahat, axborot integratsiyasi, tibbiy maslahat va boshqa tibbiy xizmatlarni taqdim etadi, bu esa bilim va ma'lumotlarning tarqalishini amalga oshiradi va shu bilan atrofdagi aholining sog'lig'iga fazoviy tarqalish ta'sirini keltirib chiqaradi.

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